

Review

Proteins that sense cellular environments – examples and implications

Snezana DJORDJEVIC

Research Department of Structural and Molecular Biology, ISMB, Division of Biosciences. University College London, Gower Street, Darwin Building, London, WC1E 6BT, UK.

Received: 15 August 2019 / Accepted: 27 August 2019 / Published Online: 8 November 2019

Summary. The first step in the process of signal perception and transduction involves interaction between a stimulus and the specific protein that has the capacity to recognise the stimulus and to translate the interaction to the physical manifestation of a signal. The physical manifestation of the signal involves what is commonly referred to as a ‘protein conformational change’ that results in a change in a conformational equilibrium of the proteins that perceive the stimuli. Reflecting on our work, here I describe two specific examples of stimuli perception and signal transduction mechanisms, one relating to the protein AioX that is found in a prokaryotic organism adapted to living under conditions of arsenic contamination, and the second example involving neuropilins - transmembrane proteins of significance for human health.

Keywords: signal transduction, AioX, neuropilins, VEGF.

INTRODUCTION

All cells must respond to their environment. Bacterial organisms, in particular, rely on their capacity to sense varieties of stimuli that are of the essence for their survival, such as the presence of nutrients or deleterious chemicals. In a multicellular organism, activities of different cells and organs need to be coordinated in the range of timescales and distances (Williamson 2012). In both instances (single cell versus multicellular organisms) evolution has led to the development of specific signalling pathways that enable cellular communication, coordination and responses. In addition to the simple, so-called one component signalling proteins, bacteria have also developed more complex two-component signalling systems, comprising a transmembrane sensory histidine kinase and an intracellular response regulator protein

that frequently exhibits DNA-binding activity and regulates transcription (Stock et al. 2000). More complex organisms contain more complex signal transduction pathways with multitude of proteins involved and controlled by the range of regulatory mechanisms (Laub 2016). Interestingly, many of the proteins that are involved in signalling contain a common subset of structural domains whose topology is found in both prokaryotic and eukaryotic proteins (Ulrich et al. 2005; Borziak and Zhulin 2007; Mayer 2015). In part this is due to the need to provide solutions for common problems associated with signalling, such as overcoming the membrane barrier via receptor dimerization (Lemmon and Schlessinger 2010) or transmembrane helix rotation (Fleishman et al. 2002). There is a plethora of other molecular mechanisms that signalling proteins and signalling pathways might use: co-localisation of proteins or combinations of domains en-

able regulation and specificity (Mayer 2015); use of common protein scaffolds with subtle modification or embellishments on their connecting loops also provide specificity; engagement of protein hubs and adaptor proteins help bring multiple interacting proteins together (Ota et al. 2016; Yablonski 2019); posttranslational modifications such as phosphorylation, lipidation and glycosylation (Campbell et al. 2019). The following examples will serve as a framework for discussion and provide insights into the ways by which some of these mechanistic and functional aspects are embedded in specific signalling systems.

AIOX AND RHIZOBIUM NT-26

Arsenic is a potent carcinogen that poses a significant threat to ecological and public health globally (Ratnaik 2003). While the immediate effects of acute arsenic poisoning include skin changes, vomiting, stomach cramps and diarrhoea, persistent exposure results in a multi-system disease with malignancies as the most lethal consequence. Currently, there are no approved treatments for chronic arsenic poisoning and management of toxicity is focused on reducing arsenic ingestion from drinking water. Therefore, there is a clear need for more detailed understanding of the carcinogenic mechanisms of arsenic as well as for the development of biological sensors that would facilitate rapid, selective and non-toxic detection of arsenic contamination in the environment and within cells (Soleja et al. 2019).

Even though arsenic is toxic to most organisms, there are prokaryotic organisms that have been isolated from arsenic-contaminated environments. Characterisation of these organisms have demonstrated that, to various degrees, they have adapted to living in these hostile environments by evolving molecular machineries that are engaged not only in detoxification and tolerance but also in exploitation of arsenic as an energy source (Santini et al. 2000; Oremland et al. 2002). Arsenite oxidase (Aio) is the best characterised arsenic-metabolising enzyme (Ellis et al. 2001; Warelow et al. 2013). Aio, isolated from aerobic organisms, comprises two subunits, AioA - molybden-dependent, also containing a 3Fe-4S cluster and AioB - Rieske [2Fe-2S]-containing subunit (Ellis et al. 2001).

In *Proteobacteria*, expression of Aio is regulated by a three-gene cluster adjacent to the arsenite oxidase genes (Kashyap et al. 2006; Sardiwal et al. 2010; Liu et al. 2012). Two of the genes from the cluster, *aioS* and *aioR*, comprise a cognate sensory histidine kinase/response regulator pair. We have characterised the functional properties of *aioS* and *aioR* from the chemolithoautotrophic *Rhizobium* sp. str. NT-26 (NT-26 for short) (Sardiwal et al. 2010). The kinase protein AioS exhibits a typical histidine kinase topology with a periplasmic domain, flanked by two transmembrane helices and

linked to intracellular HAMP and kinase domains. The response regulator protein is a transcription regulator belonging to the AAA+ family of s^{54} -dependent regulators. The two proteins are required for arsenite oxidase expression and arsenite oxidation. However, functioning of this apparently canonical bacterial two-component signal transduction system depends on a third protein component, which is encoded by the *aioX* gene – the third gene in the regulatory cluster. In *Rhizobium* sp. str. NT-26, *aioX* is positioned upstream of *aioS* and the three genes are co-transcribed but on a separate transcriptional unit from that of *aioAB* (Sardiwal et al. 2010).

Recently we reported three-dimensional crystal structures of AioX in an apo, phosphate and arsenite-bound state and we compared its ligand-binding properties with that of homologues from other organisms (Badilla et al. 2018). Characterisation of these proteins allowed us to identify a new subfamily of arsenic oxyanion-binding proteins involved in regulation of bioenergetic arsenic metabolism. The periplasmic binding proteins in this structural family originate from phylogenetically distant bacteria, they exhibit exquisite substrate selectivity, and could be developed into powerful sensors for toxic arsenic oxyanions.

Three-dimensional structure of AioX

AioX is a 304-residues long polypeptide that folds into two similar a/b domains organised in a typical bilobed structure that is characteristic of class II periplasmic (substrate) binding proteins (Fukami-Kobayashi et al. 1999). Each subdomain comprises a mixed beta-sheet, with only one strand antiparallel to the rest in each of the subdomains (PDBID: 6ESK). The two structural halves of AioX are linked by two extended crossing-over peptide linkers. At the C-terminus, the canonical fold is extended by an additional (6th) beta strand within the first beta-sheet and the terminal helix. The three-dimensional structure of AioX is highly similar to that of the *E. coli* phosphonate-binding protein PhnD (Alicia et al. 2011), with which AioX shares 25% amino acid sequence identity. In this class of proteins a ligand-binding pocket is characteristically located in the space between the two sub-domains and when the initial electron density maps for the crystals generated in a phosphate-containing buffer were examined, we were able to unambiguously identify electron density consistent with the presence of a phosphate ion (PDBID: ESV) at the inter-domain interface. Superposition of the AioX from NT-26 with the phosphonate-bound structure of *E. coli* PhnD further reinforced identification of a substrate-binding site within AioX, because the coordinates of the AioX-bound phosphate and the PhnD-bound phosphonate partially overlapped (Badilla et al. 2018). The phosphate ion, a chemical mimetic of arsenite, was positioned near the AioX-specific residue Cys106 in the puta-

tive ligand-binding site, thereby suggesting that this unique cysteine might be involved in binding arsenite.

The crystal structure of an arsenite-bound AioX validated Cys106 as an essential residue (PDBID: 6EU7). Namely, the structure clearly showed covalent linkage between the arsenite ion and the sulphur atom of Cys106 side chain. The structures for the three forms of AioX (apo, phosphate- and arsenite-bound) also allowed for examining the atomic-level features of the ligand-binding site and for identifying global conformational differences specifically associated with the presence of arsenite. The most pronounced differences in the conformation of the polypeptide backbone were detected in the structure of the arsenite-bound form, where attachment of arsenite to Cys106 was associated with hydrophobic collapse of the residues forming the main loop (residues 53–61) at the edge of one of the subdomains, and thus resulting in a subtle closure of the ligand-binding site (Fig. 1). Importantly, the conformational rearrangement had direct impact on the molecular surface and the surface electrostatic potential of AioX. This direct manifestation of ligand-binding will inevitably change the nature of protein/protein interactions between AioX and the periplasmic domain of the AioS sensory kinase, leading to its activation and downstream regulation.

But how did arsenite binding ‘cause’ this conformational change? Close inspection of the residues surrounding bound arsenite shows that residue Tyr88 plays a unique function,

Fig. 1. Comparison of the apo form of AioX (yellow) and the arsenite-bound (pink). In the crystal, arsenite is covalently linked to cysteine C106. Arsenite-binding causes a side chain rotamer change at Y88 in concert with a large backbone conformational change spanning residues 53–61 (circled in the figure). While the apo and arsenite-bound form exhibited distinct conformations of this loop, the electron density for the corresponding region in the phosphate-bound AioX crystal structure was very disordered, suggesting higher flexibility of the loop for the phosphate-bound form.

such that it adopts two different rotamer conformations depending on the presence of a ligand. Most likely the two distinct Tyr88 rotamer conformations and the two different AioX global conformations represent the hallmarks of these two extreme states in the conformational equilibrium, with one of the states stabilised by arsenite binding. Indeed, the crystal structures show that Tyr88 rotamer observed in the apo form of AioX and the specific conformation of the ligand-binding site loop, as observed in the arsenite-bound AioX, are mutually sterically exclusive. In other words, loop closure by rearrangement of hydrophobic residues (hydrophobic collapse) can only occur if Tyr88 adopts a rotamer orientation that is consistent with arsenite-binding. Interestingly, even though we were able to detect a phosphate ion in one of the determined AioX crystal structures, suggesting that the phosphate ion mimics arsenite-binding, phosphate-binding did not sufficiently stabilise the ligand-binding loop and the corresponding electron density was disordered (Badilla et al. 2018). Apart from the Tyr88 rotamer, overall the phosphate-bound structure had more similarity to the apo rather than the arsenite-bound form of AioX.

Conserved and unique features of AioX-binding pocket have implications for signalling mechanism of AioX

Alignment of the amino acid sequence of AioX with that of the close homologues ArrX, ArxX and PhnD, identified conserved residues in the AioX subfamily of periplasmic binding proteins (for details see Badilla et al. 2018). These residues, corresponding to Tyr88, Cys106, Tyr131, Ser161, Ser163, His192 and Asp210 in AioX, indicate an evolutionary and functional relationship linked to similar substrate-binding capabilities. Differences among the polypeptides, such as the absence of Cys106 in PhnD, and the presence of the specific hydrophobic loop residues in AioX, point towards the structural requirements for arsenite binding. Isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) experiments demonstrated the distinct substrate specificity of these proteins, confirming AioX as a protein with the highest affinity for arsenite ($K_d=170$ nM) while ArrX selectively bound arsenate (As(V)) with a micromolar affinity. Structural studies and the ligand-binding experiments jointly suggested that the conserved binding residues alone were not sufficient to confer full ligand specificity and that additional region in the polypeptide, affecting overall conformation of the protein, plays a profound role in selectivity. With consideration of the significant conformational changes that impact the shape and electrostatic potential of the molecular surface of AioX upon arsenite binding we could postulate signalling mechanisms analogous to mechanisms seen previously for proteins LuxP and TorT (Neiditch et al. 2006; Baraquet et al. 2006; Moore and Hendrickson 2012). The two proteins

form complexes with the sensory domains from their specific histidine kinases, LuxQ and TorS respectively, and kinase activation/repression is linked to the symmetrical/asymmetrical state of the kinase complexes, regulated by the specific ligand binding to LuxP and TorT. In AioX, similarly, the new molecular surface generated by arsenite-binding would be a trigger of a putative symmetry/asymmetry switch associated with AioS activation. High affinity and selectivity of AioX, together with its molecular dynamic characteristics, enable rapid response to arsenite and these molecular properties could provide a unique platform for the development of a new type of a biosensor.

NEUROFILINS

As a second example of signalling proteins, I will comment on neuropilins. Neuropilins (NRP1/NRP2) are transmembrane proteins with a pivotal role in key physiological processes, including: vasculogenesis, angiogenesis, lymphangiogenesis, axonal guidance, and immunomodulation (Parker et al. 2012; Djordjevic and Driscoll 2013; Roy et al. 2017). They are essential for development, but are also implicated in pathologies such as various cancers and proliferative neuropathies. Role of neuropilins have been demonstrated in many cancers; an autocrine VEGF₁₆₅-dependent signalling mechanism promotes breast cancer (Bachelder et al. 2001); preclinical studies support a role for NRP1 in lung and renal cancer cell migration, proliferation and invasion (Castro-Rivera et al. 2004; Hong et al. 2007; Cao et al. 2008); NRP1 is essential in skin tumorigenesis – NRP1 deletion abrogates the response of cancer stem cells to autocrine VEGF (Beck et al. 2011). NRP2 is implicated in colon cancer, prostate cancer and triple negative breast cancer (Elaimy et al. 2019); NRP1 supports proliferation of human glioma stem-like cells in glioblastoma multiforme (Hamerlik et al. 2012). All of these functions result from neuropilins' interactions with a plethora of ligands. Neuropilin-1 (NRP1) was initially discovered as a neuronal adhesion molecule in the retinectal projection of *Xenopus* tadpoles (Takagi et al. 1987). NRP1 was specifically identified as a receptor for the class III semaphorin SEMA3A, and this interaction was associated with a collapse of neuronal growth cones (Kolodkin et al. 1997). Since then, neuropilins have been shown to also interact with class IV semaphorins, HGF, PDGF, EGF, integrins, cell-cell adhesion receptors, galectins, TGF-beta (reviewed in Parker et al. 2012). But the best characterised interaction is that with various forms of VEGF with the direct implications for angiogenesis and immunomodulation.

Three-dimensional structure of neuropilins – conserved features

Neuropilins are type one transmembrane proteins. They contain an ectodomain region which consists of five distinct structural domains, a single transmembrane helix and a short 44-residues long intracellular region. The extracellular domains are named **a1**, **a2**, **b1**, **b2** and **c**. Domains **a1** and **a2** are structurally homologous to one another and have the beta-sandwich topology of the so-called CUB structural domains (Nakamura et al. 1998; Appleton et al., 2007). The CUB domain structural motif is utilised to carry out a wide range of functions, but primarily in the context of extracellular or plasma membrane proteins. In neuropilins, these CUB domains are required for interaction with semaphorins. Neuropilin domains **b1** and **b2** also have a beta-strand based fold and belong to the family of coagulation factor V/ VIII type C domains or discoidin structural family. In neuropilins, while both **b1** and **b2** domains are required for maintaining receptor integrity, a series of functional and structural studies have demonstrated that it is the specific site on the **b1** domain that engages with VEGFs C-terminal end (Vander Kooi et al. 2007; Tsai et al. 2016). The membrane proximal **c** domain is also referred to as a MAM domain owing to its similarity to domains found in meprin, A5, and receptor protein tyrosine phosphatase mu (Takagi et al. 1991; Beckmann and Bork 1993). MAM domains also form a stable beta structure known as a jellyroll topology. Several research groups, including ours, have investigated the detailed atomic structure of the first four extracellular domains, and their complexes with biological or small molecule ligands (Lee et al. 2002; Appleton et al. 2007; Vander Kooi et al. 2007; Jarvis et al. 2010; Parker et al. 2012b, Tsai et al. 2016; Mota et al. 2018). More recently, we reported that a crystal structure of the MAM domain of NRP1 comprises a variable N-terminal region with a short alpha helix connected through an extensive linker to a single beta strand, and an adjacent 8-stranded beta-barrel, followed by a short alpha-helical turn at the C-terminus (Yelland and Djordjevic 2016). The structure was stabilised by a specific Ca²⁺ binding site. Thus, all of the neuropilins' extracellular domains adopt some type of stable beta-structures that have been found in other extracellular-domain containing proteins. The presence of these domains provides neuropilins with the multiple surfaces for interactions with various ligands and protein partners, which is why neuropilins are frequently referred to as pluripotent receptors.

A single transmembrane helix connects this large ectopic domain with the intracellular domain containing the terminal 44 residues. Our knowledge with respect to the structure of the intracellular region is limited and all of the current experimental evidence, including NMR spectroscopy, indicates that this part of the polypeptide can be described as

intrinsically disordered, at least when not engaged in interactions with other partner proteins (unpublished data).

VEGF receptor complexes and the role of neuropilins in mediating response to VEGFs

Best characterised interactions of neuropilins are those with vascular endothelial growth factor VEGF. However, even describing interactions with this ‘single’ ligand is intrinsically complex – namely in humans there are several VEGF genes: VEGFA, VEGFB, VEGFC, VEGFD, which either exist as splice variants or are subject to posttranslational proteolytic processing (Eichmann and Simons 2012). Physiologically, perhaps most significant is VEGFA with VEGFA₁₆₅ (here 165 refers to the number of amino acids) being its most abundant splice variant and comprising regions encoded by exons 2-5, exon 7 and a short 6-residues long sequence at the C-terminus encoded by exon 8.

VEGFs mediate their function primarily via the family of VEGF receptors (VEGF-Rs), which are classical tyrosine kinases whose activation mechanisms involve ligand-induced dimerization, thereby enabling tyrosine phosphorylation. However, neuropilins play a profound role in stabilizing this complex and enhancing tyrosine kinase activity. Figure 2 shows the putative organisation of a ternary complex formed

by VEGF₁₆₅, VEGF-R2 and NRP1. While the structures of nearly all of the components of this complex have now been determined, the actual three-dimensional structure of the full receptors-ligand assembly is still not known. For illustrative purposes, the image of the complex was constructed with consideration of restraints imposed by knowing the partial structures, the size of the individual components, and by the knowledge of the relative orientations of the individual domains, within the proteins and with respect to the cellular membrane. The core region of a dimeric, disulphide bridged VEGF molecule is bound to a dimer of the VEGF receptor, via interactions with immunoglobulin homology domains 2 and 3 (Leppanen et al. 2010). Terminal 55 residues, provide a positively charged, heparin-binding (HBD domain) (Parker et al. 2012) linked to an adjacent neuropilin molecule with the C-terminus of HBD specifically interacting with the ligand-binding groove on neuropilin’s **b1**-domain. In the illustration, for simplicity, only a single neuropilin molecule was included; however it is known that neuropilins can dimerise, particularly in the presence of heparin. Previously, molecular biology data suggested that the function of the membrane proximal *c*/MAM domain of neuropilins might be in mediating dimerization (Nakamura et al. 1998). However, our work has shown that the MAM domain from NRP1

Fig. 2. Putative model of a ternary assembly between the ectodomains of neuropilin (dark gold) and VEGF receptor (grey) with the dimeric VEGF molecule (salmon red). The illustration is showing molecular surfaces generated from the crystal structures and combined as described in the text. A: The ternary complex. B: Molecular surface of the NRP1-b1 domain in complex with antagonist EG01377 shown as sticks and coloured based on the atoms. C: The same as in B but rotated by 90 degrees providing the view from the top of the complex showing how EG01377 competes for binding with the C-terminus of VEGF.

is monomeric in solution and insufficient to drive receptor dimerization (Yelland and Djordjevic 2016). We postulated that the MAM domain in the context of neuropilins, shields the ectodomain from the membrane surface and positions other domains (**a1a2b1b2**) for their interactions with partner co-receptors. This domain might also modulate multimerization and organisation of the higher order receptor clusters, which could have implication for signalling by supporting cooperativity and modulating signal to noise ratios of the signalling complexes. Additionally, as the N-terminal region of the c/MAM domain is subject to O-linked glycosylation (Windwarder et al. 2015), this domain might mediate interactions with other binding partners, such as galectins and modifying enzymes.

So, how do neuropilins 'signal' and how is their activity regulated? As already mentioned, neuropilins do not have catalytic activity and they are perceived to function as 'co-receptors' together with VEGF-Rs in order to mediate response to VEGFs. The name 'neuropilins' primarily refers to two proteins: NRP1 and NRP2, and while they share 44% sequence identity they are characterised by differences in expression patterns and ligand preferences and thus they play different physiological roles. NRP1 is for example localized preferentially in arteries. In contrast, NRP2 is expressed preferentially in veins and lymphatic endothelial cells (Hercog et al. 2001). This differential expression parallels differences in physiological responses to the main ligands such that NRP1 is considered to be a primary receptor for VEGFA while NRP2 mediates responses to VEGFC. The intracellular C-terminal region of neuropilins is also required for a full signalling response, in particular the terminal -SEA sequence motif, which interacts with the PDZ domain of the scaffolding protein GIPC/Synectin. This SEA sequence motif is indispensable for the full signalling function of neuropilins, as well as for the coupling of neuropilins' with integrins, and is important for cell migration (Prahts et al. 2008; Robinson et al. 2009). It should also be recognized that neuropilins are subject to extensive modifications by glycans – NRP1 is a substrate for chondroitin sulphate addition, NRP2 is a subject to polysialylation (Shintani et al. 2006; Frankel et al. 2008; Bhide et al. 2016). While addition of these large polar molecules will inevitably have a dramatic effect on neuropilins' capacity to form protein/protein interactions, the full extent by which these modifications control signalling outputs is poorly understood.

Targeting neuropilins

In light of neuropilins' role in angiogenesis, cell migration and maintenance of cancer cell stemness, as well as in immunomodulation, there is substantial merit in producing therapeutics to this pleiotropic target. Importantly, studies

have shown that targeting these molecules would provide an effective means for tumour growth inhibition, while decreasing resistance to other therapies (Goel et al. 2013; Mercurio 2019). There are several areas of neuropilin molecules and the receptor assembly that could be targeted, but the most explored and most effective approach so far involves development of small-molecule antagonists that target the well-described VEGF C-terminus binding-site on the **b1** domain. Using a range of structural studies, in vitro experiments, functional assays and proof-of-concept studies, it was shown that the main tool compounds, EG00229 and EG01377 bind to the **b1** domain of NRP1 selectively, that they inhibit VEGF receptor tyrosine kinase phosphorylation and associated VEGF-mediated functions such as angiogenesis and cell-migration (Jarvis et al. 2010; Miyauchi et al. 2016; Powell et al. 2018). Crucially, the compounds were shown to be effective in mice glioma models where they suppressed glioma progression and their activity was linked to the function of microglia, macrophages and Treg cells.

FINAL COMMENTS AND GENERAL CONCLUSIONS

Proteins involved in receiving and responding to environmental signals exhibit structural features that are shared across the domains of life. Commonality of structural domains is the evolutionary consequence of the requirements for the molecular plasticity and molecular dynamics of the proteins and molecular mechanisms employed to carry out these functions. The presence of these common structural threads and many of the global functional and mechanistic features allow us to transpose the knowledge gained from one signalling system to another. However, unique functional and structural properties of each of the molecular interactions necessitate detailed characterisation of each protein, and protein complexes involved, in order to fully understand the signalling processes and their regulatory outcomes. Ultimately, this detailed understanding could be exploited for the development of new reagents, devices and therapies.

REFERENCES

- Alicea I, Marvin JS, Miklos AE, Ellington AD, Looger LL, Schreiter ER. 2011. Structure of the *Escherichia coli* phosphonate binding protein PhnD and rationally optimized phosphonate biosensors. *Journal of Molecular Biology*. 414(3):356–369.
- Appleton B, Wu P, Maloney J, Yin J, Liang W-C, Stawicki S, Mortara K, Bowman KK, Elliott JM, Desmarais W, et al. 2007. Structural studies of neuropilin/antibody complexes provide insights into semaphorin and VEGF binding. *EMBO Journal*. 26:4902–4912.
- Bachelder RE, Crago A, Chung J, Wendt MA, Shaw LM,

- Robinson G, Mercurio AM. 2001. Vascular endothelial growth factor is an autocrine survival factor for neuropilin-expressing breast carcinoma cells. *Cancer Research*. 61:5736–5740.
- Badilla C, Osborne TH, Cole A, Watson C, Djordjevic S, Santini JM. 2018. A new family of periplasmic-binding proteins that sense arsenic oxyanions. *Scientific Reports* 8:6282.
- Baraquet C, Théraulaz L, Guiral M, Lafitte D, Méjean V, Jourlin-Castelli C. 2006. TorT, a member of a new periplasmic binding protein family, triggers induction of the Tor respiratory system upon trimethylamine N -oxide electron-acceptor binding in *Escherichia coli*. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. 281:38189–38199.
- Beck, B, Driessens G, Goossens S, Youssef KK, Kuchnio A, Caauwe A, Sotiropoulou PA, Loge S, Lapouge G, Candi A, et al. 2011. A vascular niche and a VEGF-Nrp1 loop regulate the initiation and stemness of skin tumours. *Nature*. 478:399–403.
- Beckmann G, Bork P. 1993. An adhesive domain detected in functionally diverse receptors. *Trends in Biochemical Sciences*. 18(2):40–41.
- Bhide GP, Fernandes NRJ, Colley KJ. 2016. Sequence requirements for neuropilin-2 recognition by ST8SialV and polysialylation of its O-Glycans. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. 291(18):9444–9457.
- Campbell IW, Zhou X, Amon A. 2019. The mitotic exit network integrates temporal and spatial signals by distributing regulation across multiple components. *Elife*. 8:e41139.
- Cao Y, Wang L, Nandy D, Zhang Y, Basu A, Radisky D, Mukhopadhyay D. 2008. Neuropilin-1 upholds dedifferentiation and propagation phenotypes of renal cell carcinoma cells by activating Akt and sonic hedgehog axes. *Cancer Research*. 68:8667–8672.
- Castro-Rivera E, Ran S, Thorpe P, Minna JD. 2004. Semaphorin 3B (SEMA3B) induces apoptosis in lung and breast cancer, whereas VEGF165 antagonizes this effect. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences USA*. 101:11432–11437.
- Djordjevic S, Driscoll PC. 2013. Targeting VEGF signaling via the neuropilin co-receptor. *Drug Discovery Today*. 18:447–455.
- Eichmann A, Simons M. 2012. VEGF signaling inside vascular endothelial cells and beyond. *Current Opinion in Cell Biology*. 24(2):188–193.
- Elaimy AL, Amante JJ, Zhu LJ, Wang M, Walmsley CS, FitzGerald TJ, Goel HL, Mercurio AM. 2019. The VEGF receptor neuropilin 2 promotes homologous recombination by stimulating YAP/TAZ-mediated Rad51 expression. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences USA*. 116(28):14174–14180.
- Ellis PJ, Conrads T, Hille R, Kuhn P. 2001. Crystal structure of the 100 kDa arsenite oxidase from *Alcaligenes faecalis* in two crystal forms at 1.64 Å and 2.03 Å. *Structure* 9:125–1232.
- Fleishman SJ, Schlessinger J, Ben-Tal N. 2002. A putative molecular-activation switch in the transmembrane domain of erb B2. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences USA*. 99:15937–15940.
- Fukami-Kobayashi K, Tateno Y, Nishikawa K. 1999. Domain dislocation: a change of core structure in periplasmic binding proteins in their evolutionary history. *Journal of Molecular Biology*. 286(1):279–290.
- Hamerlik P, Lathia JD, Rasmussen R, Wu Q, Bartkova J, Lee M, Moudry P, Bartek J Jr, Fischer W, Lukas J, et al. 2012. Autocrine VEGF-VEGFR2-Neuropilin-1 signaling promotes glioma stem-like cell viability and tumor growth. *Journal of Experimental Medicine*. 209:507–520.
- Frankel P, Pellet-Many C, Lehtolainen P, D'Abaco GM, Tickner ML, Cheng L, Zachary IC. 2008. Chondroitin sulphate-modified neuropilin 1 is expressed in human tumour cells and modulates 3D invasion in the U87MG human glioblastoma cell line through a p130Cas-mediated pathway. *EMBO Reports*. 9:983–989.
- Goel HL, Pursell B, Chang C, Shaw LM, Mao J, Simin K, Kumar P, Vander Kooi CW, Shultz LD, Greiner DL, et al. 2013. GLI1 regulates a novel neuropilin-2/alpha6beta1 integrin based autocrine pathway that contributes to breast cancer initiation. *EMBO Molecular Medicine*. 5:488–508.
- Hercog Y, Kalcheim C, Kahane N, Reshef R, Neufeld G. 2001. Differential expression of neuropilin-1 and neuropilin-2 in arteries and veins. *Mechanisms of Development*. 109(1):115–119.
- Hong TM, Chen YL, Wu YY, Yuan A, Chao YC, Chung YC, Wu MH, Yang SC, Pan SH, Shih JY, Chan WK, Yang PC. 2007. Targeting neuropilin 1 as an antitumor strategy in lung cancer. *Clinical Cancer Research*. 13:4759–4768.
- Jarvis A, Allerston CK, Jia H, Herzog B, Garza-Garcia A, Winfield N, Ellard K, Aqil R, Lynch R, Chapman C, et al. 2010. Small molecule inhibitors of the neuropilin-1 vascular endothelial growth factor A (VEGF-A) interaction. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*. 53:2215–2226.
- Kashyap DR, Botero LM, Franck WL, Hassett DJ, McDermott TR. 2006. Complex regulation of arsenite oxidation in *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*. *Journal of Bacteriology*. 188:1081–1088.
- Kirill Borziak K, Zhulin IB. 2007. FIST: a sensory domain for diverse signal transduction pathways in prokaryotes and ubiquitin signaling in eukaryotes. *Bioinformatics*. 23(19):2518–2521.
- Kolodkin AL, Levengood DV, Rowe EG, Tai Y-T, Giger RJ, Ginty DD. 1997. Neuropilin is a Semaphorin III receptor. *Cell*. 90(4):753–762.
- Laub MT. 2016. Keeping signals straight: How cells process information and make decisions. *PLoS Biology*. 14(7):e1002519.
- Lee C, McMullan D, Kreusch A, Ng K, Spraggon G. 2002. Crystal structure of the human neuropilin-1 b1 domain. *Structure*. 11:98–108.
- Lemmon MA, Schlessinger J. 2010. Cell signaling by receptor tyrosine kinases. *Cell*. 141:1117–1134.
- Leppänen V-M, Prota AE, Jeltsch M, Anisimov A, Kalkkinen N, Strandin T, Lankinen H, Goldman A, Ballmer-Hofer K, Alitalo K. 2010. Structural determinants of growth factor binding and specificity by VEGF receptor 2. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences USA*. 107(6):2425–2430.
- Liu G, Liu M, Kim EH, Maaty WS, Bothner B, Lei B, Rensing C, Wang G, McDermott TR. 2012. A periplasmic arsenite-binding protein involved in regulating arsenite oxidation. *Environmental Microbiology*. 14:1624–1634.
- Mayer BJ. 2015. The discovery of modular binding domains: building blocks of cell signalling. *Nature Reviews Molecular*

- Cell Biology. 16(11):691–698.
- Mercurio AM. 2019. VEGF/Neuropilin signaling in cancer stem cells. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. 20(3):490.
- Miyauchi JT, Chen D, Choi M, Nissen JC, Shroyer KR, Djordjevic S, Zachary IC, Selwood D, Tsirka SE. 2016. Ablation of Neuropilin 1 from glioma-associated microglia and macrophages slows tumor progression. *Oncotarget*. 7(9):9801–9814.
- Moore JO, Hendrickson WA. 2012. An asymmetry-to-symmetry switch in signal transmission by the histidine kinase receptor for TMAO. *Structure*. 20(4):729–741.
- Mota F, Fotinou C, Rana RR, Chan AWE, Yelland T, Arooz MT, O'Leary AP, Hutton J, Frankel P, Zachary I, Selwood D, Djordjevic S. 2018. Architecture and hydration of the arginine-binding site of neuropilin-1. *FEBS Journal*. 285:1290–1304.
- Nakamura F, Tanaka M, Takahashi T, Kalb RG, Strittmatter SM. 1998. Neuropilin-1 extracellular domains mediate semaphorin D/III-induced growth cone collapse. *Neuron*. 21:1093–1100.
- Neiditch MB, Federle MJ, Pompeani AJ, Kelly RC, Swem DL, Jeffrey PD, Bassler BL, Hughson FM. 2006. Ligand-induced asymmetry in histidine sensor kinase complex regulates quorum sensing. *Cell*. 126:1095–1108.
- Oremland RS, Hoelt SE, Santini JM, Bano N, Hollibaugh RA, Hollibaugh JT. 2002. Anaerobic oxidation of arsenite in Mono Lake water and by a facultative, arsenite-oxidizing chemoautotroph, strain MLHE-1. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*. 68:4795–4802.
- Ota M, Gonja H, Koike R, Fukuchi S. 2016. Multiple-localization and hub proteins. *PLoS One*. 11(6):e0156455.
- Parker MW, Guo HF, Li X, Linkugel AD, Vander Kooi CW. 2012. Function of the neuropilin family as essential pleiotropic cell surface receptors. *Biochemistry*. 51:9437–9446.
- Parker MW, Xu P, Li X, Vander Kooi CW. 2012. Structural basis for selective vascular endothelial growth factor-A (VEGF-A) binding to neuropilin-1. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. 287:11082–11089.
- Powell J, Mota F, Steadman D, Soudy C, Miyauchi JT, Crosby S, Jarvis A, Reisinger T, Winfield N, Evans G, et al. 2018. Small molecule neuropilin-1 antagonists combine antiangiogenic and antitumor activity with immune modulation through reduction of transforming growth factor beta (TGF β) production in regulatory T-cells. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*. 61(9):4135–4154.
- Praht C, Heroult M, Lanahan AA, Uziel N, Kessler O, Shraga-Heled N, Simons M, Neufeld G, Augustin HG. 2008. Neuropilin-1-VEGFR-2 complexing requires the PDZ-binding domain of neuropilin-1. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*. 283:25110–25114.
- Ratnaik RN. 2003. Acute and chronic arsenic toxicity. *Postgraduate Medical Journal*. 79(933):391–396.
- Roy S, Bag AK, Singh RK, Talmadge JE, Batra SK, Datta K. 2017. Multifaceted role of neuropilins in the immune system: Potential targets for immunotherapy. *Frontier in Immunology*. 8:1228.
- Robinson SD, Reynolds LE, Kostourou V, Reynolds AR, da Silva RG, Tavora B, Baker M, Marshall JF, Hodivala-Dilke KM. 2009. α v β 3 integrin limits the contribution of neuropilin-1 to vascular endothelial growth factor-induced angiogenesis. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. 284:33966–33981.
- Santini JM, Sly LI, Schnagl RD, Macy JM. 2000. A new chemolithoautotrophic arsenite-oxidizing bacterium isolated from a gold mine: phylogenetic, physiological, and preliminary biochemical studies. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*. 66:92–97.
- Sardiwal S, Santini JM, Osborne TH, Djordjevic S. 2010. Characterization of a two-component signal transduction system that controls arsenite oxidation in the chemolithoautotroph NT-26. *FEMS Microbiology Letters*. 313:20–28.
- Shintani Y, Takashima S, Asano Y, Kato H, Liao Y, Yamazaki S, Tsukamoto O, Seguchi O, Yamamoto H, Fukushima T, et al. 2006. Glycosaminoglycan modification of neuropilin-1 modulates VEGFR2 signaling. *EMBO Journal*. 25(13):3045–3055.
- Soleja N, Manzoor O, Khan P, Mohsin M. 2019. Engineering genetically encoded FRET-based nanosensors for real time display of arsenic (As³⁺) dynamics in living cells. *Scientific Reports*. 9:11240.
- Stock AM, Robinson VL, Goudreau PN. 2000. Two-component signal transduction. *Annual Reviews in Biochemistry*. 69:183–215.
- Takagi S, Tsuji T, Amagai T, Takamatsu T, Fujisawa H. 1987. Specific cell surface labels in the visual centers of *Xenopus laevis* tadpole identified using monoclonal antibodies. *Developmental Biology*. 122(1):90–100.
- Takagi S, Hirata T, Agata K, Eguchi G, Fujisawa H, Mochii M. 1991. The A5 antigen, a candidate for the neuronal recognition molecule, has homologies to complement components and coagulation factors. *Neuron*. 7(2):295–307.
- Tsai Y-CI, Fotinou C, Rana R, Yelland T, Frankel P, Zachary I, Djordjevic S. 2016. Structural studies of neuropilin-2 reveal a zinc ion binding site away from the vascular endothelial growth factor binding pocket. *FEBS Journal*. 283:1924–1934.
- Ulrich LE, Koonin EV, Zhulin IB. 2005. One-component systems dominate signal transduction in prokaryotes. *Trends in Microbiology*. 13(2):52–56.
- Vander Kooi CW, Jusino MA, Perman B, Neau DB, Bellamy HD, Leahy DJ. 2007. Structural basis for ligand and heparin binding to neuropilin B domains. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences USA*. 104:6152–6157.
- Warelow TP, Oke M, Schoepp-Cothenet B, Dahl JU, Bruselat N, Sivalingam GN, Leimkühler S, Thalassinou K, Kappler U, Naismith JH, et al. 2013. The respiratory arsenite oxidase: structure and the role of residues surrounding the Rieske cluster. *PLoS One* 8:e72535.
- Williamson M. 2012. *How proteins work*. Abingdon: Garland Science, Taylor & Francis Group, LLC.
- Windwarder M, Yelland T, Djordjevic S, Altmann F. 2016. Detailed characterization of the O-linked glycosylation of the neuropilin-1 c/MAM-domain. *Glycoconjugate Journal*. 33:387397.
- Yablonski D. 2019. Bridging the gap: Modulatory roles of the Grb2-family adaptor, Gads, in cellular and allergic immune responses. *Frontiers in Immunology*. 10:1704.
- Yelland T, Djordjevic S. 2016. Crystal structure of the neuropilin-1 MAM domain: completing the neuropilin-1 ectodomain picture. *Structure*. 24:2008–2015.